
CHIANTI

An Astrophysical Database for Emission Line Spectroscopy

CHIANTI TECHNICAL REPORT No. 31

The CHIANTI Ion Masterlist

The CHIANTI software knows which ions are in the database through the masterlist: an ascii file that has a list of all the ions. This document describes this file, and the additional masterlist file for the advanced ion models introduced in CHIANTI 11 (Dufresne et al., 2024).

1 The masterlist file

The masterlist file is called `masterlist.ions` and is located in the directory `!xuvtop/masterlist`. It contains a list of ions using the CHIANTI format. For example, `o_6` corresponds to O VI and `fe_13` corresponds to Fe XIII. An ion name with a “d” appended indicates an ion model for dielectronic satellite lines, which were introduced in CHIANTI 3 (Dere et al., 2001). Each line in the file can contain a comment if it includes a semi-colon. Text after the semi-colon will be treated as a comment.

If a new ion is added to CHIANTI, then the name of the ion needs to be added to the masterlist otherwise the software will not be aware that the model exists.

2 Reading the masterlist

The recommended IDL routine for reading the masterlist is `ch_read_list_ions`. It will read the default masterlist as follows:

```
IDL> mlist=ch_read_list_ions()
```

The output is a structure with two tags. The tag `list_ions` contains the list of ions. The tag `nlevels` is not relevant for the default masterlist and is assigned values of -1.

To directly specify a masterlist file, the call is:

```
IDL> mlist=ch_read_list_ions(filename)
```

3 The advanced ion models

A separate masterlist contains the list of all ions for which advanced models are available. These models were introduced in CHIANTI 11, and CHIANTI Technical Report No. 32 gives more details. The advanced model masterlist is called `advmodel_list.ions` and is located in the directory `!xuvtop/ancillary_data/advanced_models`.

Like the default masterlist, the file contains a list of ions. However, for each ion there is an integer that sets the size of the ion model that is used to determine the metastable level populations. The line can also optionally contain a comment after the integer.

The advanced model masterlist can be read with `ch_read_list_ions` as follows:

```
IDL> mlist=ch_read_list_ions(/advanced)
```

The output structure tag `nlevels` contains the number of levels used for the metastable population calculation.

4 Validity check

Prior to each release of CHIANTI, the routine `ch_check_masterlist` is run, which checks the ions in masterlist against the contents of the database. In particular, it identifies if an ion in the masterlist is not represented in the database, and if an ion exists in the database but is not in the masterlist. The routine is run as:

```
IDL> ch_check_masterlist
```

For CHIANTI 11, the ions Mg I and Si I were added for the advanced model calculations and thus they are listed in the advanced masterlist. However, they are not included in the regular masterlist. This is because the ion models do not have fine structure levels, only LS levels, hence they will not yield accurate spectral line emissivities.

5 Additional routines

The legacy routine `read_masterlist` is used in several CHIANTI routines to read the masterlist, but this is being phased out in favor of `ch_read_list_ions`.

References

- Dere, K. P., Landi, E., Young, P. R., & Del Zanna, G. 2001, *ApJS*, 134, 331,
doi: <http://doi.org/10.1086/32085410.1086/320854>
- Dufresne, R. P., Del Zanna, G., Young, P. R., et al. 2024, *ApJ*, 974, 71,
doi: <http://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ad676510.3847/1538-4357/ad6765>

A Document history

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